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EPRES-BE 2023 Questionnaire, English translation.

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Start of Block: Age Gender

Q2.1 What is your age?

Q2.2 You are a...

- Woman (1)
- Man (2)
- X (3)

Start of Block: Education

Q4 What is your highest obtained diploma?

- No diploma (1)
- primary completed (2)
- Lower secondary education completed (3)
- Higher secondary education completed (4)
- College completed (5)
- University completed (7)
- PhD completed (8)

Start of Block: employment status

Q3 I am currently..

- Employed as an employee (with or without second job) (1)
- Temporary unemployment (10)
- Disabled/disabled (2)
- Incapacitated for work with progressive employment (3)
- Retired (also early retirement, early retirement and unemployment with company supplement) (4)
- Housewife/Houseman (5)
- Unemployed with benefits (6)
- Unemployed without benefits (7)
- Self-employed (or artist) (8)
- Others: (9) _____

Start of Block: Sector

The following questions are about the circumstances at your work. Think of your main paid job when answering.

Q8 Indicate the industry you work in.

- Agriculture and Fisheries (1)
 - Industry (2)
 - Electricity, gas and water (3)
 - Construction sector (4)
 - Trade (5)
 - Catering industry (6)
 - Transport/Transport (7)
 - Financial sector (8)
 - Communication and computer science (9)
 - Business services to companies (consulting, surveillance, ...) (10)
 - Cleaning (no service vouchers) (11)
 - Other services (profit) (12)
 - Education, Healthcare and Government (non-profit) (13)
 - Service vouchers (14)
 - Another industry: (15) _____
-

Display This Question: only to 'Education, Healthcare and Government (non-profit)'

If Q8 = 13

Q8_2 More specifically, in which sector of Education, Health care or government do you work?

- Home help and elderly caregiver services (PC 318) (1)
- Educational and housing institutions and services (PC 319) (PC 319.01) (2)
- Healthcare facilities and services(PC 330) (3)
- Welfare and health sector (PC 332) (4)
- Other health sector (5)
- Education (6)
- Government (7)

Start of Block: occupation healthcare

Display This Question: only to healthcare

If Q8_2 = 1 OR 2 OR 3 OR 4 OR 5

Q9_1 What is your occupation in the health care sector? If your occupation is not in the list, describe it under 'Other'.

- Nurse (Master level) (1)
- Nurse (Graduate or Bachelor level) (2)
- Health care assistant (3)
- Personal care worker (4)
- Midwife (5)
- Social worker (6)
- Other (7) _____

Display This Question: only to healthcare

If Q8_2 = 1 OR 2 OR 3 OR 4 OR 5

Q9_2 In what kind of health institution do you work?

- Hospital (1)
- Nursing home/Elderly care (2)
- Public health centre (3)
- Kindergarten (4)
- Private practitioner/Self-employed (5)
- Other (6) _____

Display This Question: only to healthcare

If Q8_2 = 1 OR 2 OR 3 OR 4 OR 5

Q311 Do you work as a manager?

- No (1)
 - Yes, as an immediate manager (e.g. ward manager...) (2)
 - Yes, in middle management (e.g. head nurse...) (3)
 - Yes, in strategic management (e.g. administrative nurse...) (4)
-

Display This Question: only to non-healthcare

If Q8 = NOT 13 OR Q8_2 = 6 OR 7

Q9 Describe as specifically as possible your position in your main paid job. By main job we mean the job where you spend the most working hours.

Start of Block: permanent contract

Display This Question: not to self-employed or artists

If Q3 = NOT 8

Q10 Do you have a permanent contract with your employer?

- Yes, I have a permanent contract with this organization. (1)
- No, I do not have a permanent contract with this organization. (2)

Start of Block: type of permanent contract

Display This Question: to permanent contract and not to self-employed

If Q10 = NOT 2 AND Q3 = NOT 8

Q11 What type of contract best describes your current employment?

- contract of indefinite duration (1)
- Others: (2) _____

Start of Block: type of temporary contract

Display This Question: to temporary contract and not to self-employed

If Q10 = 2 AND Q3 = NOT 8

Q12 What type of contract best describes your current employment?

- Temporary/limited duration (1)
- Contract with an employment agency (2)
- IBO/Starter job agreement (4)
- An apprenticeship (5)
- Others: (7) _____

Start of Block: second job

Q14 Do you have other paid jobs in addition to your main paid job?

- Yes, the same job as 6 months ago (1)
- Yes, a different job than 6 months ago (4)
- No, I don't have any additional paid job(s) (2)

Start of Block: type of second job

Display This Question: to second jobs

If Q14 = 1 OR 4

Q15 Is this job/are these jobs...?

- On a permanent basis (1)
- On a non-permanent or irregular basis (2)
- Self-employed secondary activity (3)
- Flexi-job (5)
- Others: (4) _____

Start of Block: working hours

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

Q16_1 How many hours per week do you work according to your contract? (for your main paid job)

Q16_2 How many hours do you work on average per week in reality? (for your main paid job)

Display This Question: to second jobs

If Q14 = 1 OR 4

Q16_2_2 How many hours do you work on average per week in reality? (for all your paid jobs combined)

Q16_3 How many hours would you like to work per week, taking into account that your income will also increase or decrease depending on the working hours you have indicated?

Start of Block: empowerment(informal)

The following questions are again about your most important job (that is, the job in which you work the most hours).

How are the following terms of employment arranged? Think of the most common situation.

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

Q18 The work tasks of the day

- I mostly choose this myself (1)
 - In consultation between colleagues (2)
 - In personal consultation with my direct boss (3)
 - It is imposed on me without consultation (4)
 - I don't know (5)
-

Display This Question: to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = 8

Q18_z The work tasks of the day

- I mostly choose this myself (1)
 - In consultation between employees (2)
 - In personal consultation with my client (3)
 - It is imposed on me without consultation (4)
 - I don't know (5)
-

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

Q19 The weekly or monthly schedule

- I mostly choose this myself (1)
 - In consultation between colleagues (2)
 - In personal consultation with my direct boss (3)
 - It is imposed on me without consultation (4)
 - I don't know (5)
-

Display This Question: to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = 8

Q19_z The weekly or monthly schedule

- I mostly choose this myself (1)
- In consultation between employees (2)
- In personal consultation with my client (3)
- It is imposed on me without consultation (4)
- I don't know (5)

Start of Block: empowerment (formal)

How are the following terms of employment arranged? Think of the most common situation.

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

Q21 Hourly wages and salaries

- Through collective labor agreements (CLA) (1)
- Through negotiation between the employee representatives and the employer (2)
- In personal consultation with my direct boss (3)
- It is imposed on me without consultation (4)
- I don't know (5)

Display This Question: to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = 8

Q21_z The hourly wages or prices

- I largely determine it myself (1)
 - There are agreements about this within the sector or with suppliers (2)
 - In personal consultation with the customer (3)
 - It is imposed on me without consultation (4)
 - I don't know (5)
-

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

Q22 Social benefits and rights

- Through collective labor agreements (CLA) (1)
 - Through negotiation between the employee representatives and the employer (2)
 - In personal consultation with my direct boss (3)
 - It is imposed on me without consultation (4)
 - I don't know (5)
-

Start of Block: Predictability of working hours 1

Q23 Does your work schedule regularly change beyond your will?

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - No opinion (3)
-

Start of Block: Predictability of working hours 2

Display This Question: schedule changes regularly and not self-employed

If Q23 = 1 AND Q3 = NOT 8

Q24 How long before the change will you be notified?

- The same day (1)
- One day in advance (2)
- A few days in advance (3)
- A few weeks in advance (4)
- Not applicable, I have a fixed schedule (5)

End of Block: Voorspelbaarheid uren 2

Start of Block: Union representative

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

Q25 Do you know who the union representative of your workplace is?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)
- There is no union representative (3)

Start of Block: vulnerability

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

To what extent do you agree with the following statements about your relationship with **your immediate supervisor?**

Display This Question: to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = 8

To what extent do you agree with the following statements about your relationship with your customers or clients?

Q27 If I wanted better working conditions, I would be afraid to ask.

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Rather disagree (2)
 - Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
 - Mostly agree (4)
 - Completely agree (5)
 - No opinion (8)
-

Q28 If I were treated unfairly, I wouldn't dare to argue.

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Rather disagree (2)
 - Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
 - Mostly agree (4)
 - Completely agree (5)
 - No opinion (6)
-

Q29 I am treated in an authoritarian way.

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Rather disagree (2)
 - Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
 - Mostly agree (4)
 - Completely agree (5)
 - No opinion (6)
-

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

Q30 I have to worry about being fired if I don't immediately do what I'm told.

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Rather disagree (2)
 - Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
 - Mostly agree (4)
 - Completely agree (5)
 - No opinion (6)
-

Display This Question: to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = 8

Q30_z I have to worry about losing an assignment or customer if I didn't immediately do as I'm told.

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Rather disagree (2)
 - Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
 - Mostly agree (4)
 - Completely agree (5)
 - No opinion (6)
-

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

Q31 I have to worry about being fired when I temporarily do not work as well.

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Rather disagree (2)
 - Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
 - Mostly agree (4)
 - Completely agree (5)
 - No opinion (6)
-

Display This Question: to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = 8

Q31_z I have to worry about losing an assignment or customer when I temporarily do not work as well.

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Rather disagree (2)
 - Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
 - Mostly agree (4)
 - Completely agree (5)
 - No opinion (6)
-

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

Q32 I have to worry about being fired if I were to participate in a strike.

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Rather disagree (2)
 - Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
 - Mostly agree (4)
 - Completely agree (5)
 - No opinion (6)
-

Display This Question: to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = 8

Q32_z I have to worry about losing an order or customer if I were to participate in a strike.

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Rather disagree (2)
 - Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
 - Mostly agree (4)
 - Completely agree (5)
 - No opinion (6)
-

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

Q33 My bosses make me feel like I'm easily replaceable.

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Rather disagree (2)
 - Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
 - Mostly agree (4)
 - Completely agree (5)
 - No opinion (6)
-

Display This Question: to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = 8

Q33_z My clients make me feel like I'm easily replaceable.

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Rather disagree (2)
 - Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
 - Mostly agree (4)
 - Completely agree (5)
 - No opinion (6)
-

Q34 I am treated in an aggressive manner.

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Rather disagree (2)
 - Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
 - Mostly agree (4)
 - Completely agree (5)
 - No opinion (6)
-

Q35 I am being treated in an unfair or discriminatory way.

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Rather disagree (2)
 - Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
 - Mostly agree (4)
 - Completely agree (5)
 - No opinion (6)
-

Q36 I am paid enough for the work I do.

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Rather disagree (2)
 - Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
 - Mostly agree (4)
 - Completely agree (5)
 - No opinion (6)
-

Q37 I am well informed about the health and safety risks inherent to the execution of my job.

- Completely disagree (1)
- Rather disagree (2)
- Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
- Mostly agree (4)
- Completely agree (5)
- No opinion (6)

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

Q38 "The administration of my wages and working conditions (leave, premiums, travel allowance,...) is generally correct."

- Completely disagree (1)
- Rather disagree (2)
- Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
- Mostly agree (4)
- Completely agreed (5)
- No opinion (6)

Start of Block: support from supervisor and colleagues

The following questions are about the support you have received from your immediate supervisor over the past week. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

Q58 My immediate supervisor has an eye for my well-being.

- Totally agree (1)
 - Rather agree (2)
 - Rather disagree (3)
 - Completely disagree (4)
 - No opinion (5)
 - I don't have a manager (6)
-

Q59 My immediate supervisor helps me and supports me.

- Totally agree (1)
 - Rather agree (2)
 - Rather disagree (3)
 - Completely disagree (4)
 - No opinion (5)
 - I don't have a manager (6)
-

Q60 My immediate supervisor helps to get the work done.

- Totally agree (1)
 - Rather agree (2)
 - Rather disagree (3)
 - Completely disagree (4)
 - No opinion (5)
 - I don't have a manager (6)
-

Q61 My direct supervisor succeeds in getting people to work together.

- Totally agree (1)
 - Rather agree (2)
 - Rather disagree (3)
 - Completely disagree (4)
 - No opinion (5)
 - I don't have a manager (6)
-

The following questions are about the support you have received from your immediate colleagues over the past week. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

Q63 My colleagues are interested in me.

- Totally agree (1)
 - Rather agree (2)
 - Rather disagree (3)
 - Completely disagree (4)
 - No opinion (5)
 - I mainly work alone (6)
-

Q64 My colleagues are friendly.

- Totally agree (1)
 - Rather agree (2)
 - Rather disagree (3)
 - Completely disagree (4)
 - No opinion (5)
 - I mainly work alone (6)
-

Q65 My colleagues help to get the work done.

- Totally agree (1)
- Rather agree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Completely disagree (4)
- No opinion (5)
- I mainly work alone (6)

Start of Block: Psychological contract

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

Think about **the organization** you work for. To what extent do the items below describe **your employer's** relationship to you? My employer...

	Completely disagree (1)	Rather disagree (2)	Partly agree, partly disagree (3)	Mostly agree (4)	Completely agree (5)	Not applicable (7)
...shows that it does not trust me (Q305_1)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
...is unpredictable (Q305_2)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
...demands more from me while giving less in return (Q305_3)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
...fulfills its commitments to me (Q305_4)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I have fulfilled my commitments to my employer (Q305_5)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Start of Block: rights

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

Q39 I am entitled to paid vacation.

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - I don't know (3)
-

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

Q40 I am entitled to thematic leave (it can concern at least 1 of the following: paid parental leave, time credit, care leave, ...).

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - I don't know (3)
 - Does not apply (4)
-

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

Q42 I am entitled to hospitalization insurance provided by my employer.

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - I don't know (3)
-

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

Q43 I am entitled to unemployment benefits if I get fired.

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - I don't know (3)
-

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

Q44 I am entitled to at least 1 of the following fringe benefits: eco vouchers, meal vouchers, gift vouchers.

- Yes (1)
- No (2)
- I don't know (3)

Start of Block: enforceability of rights

How easy is it to actually obtain the rights mentioned below without any problem. If you do not have a certain right, answer 'not applicable'.

	Very easy (1)	Rather easy (2)	Rather difficult (3)	Very difficult (4)	No opinion (5)	Does not apply (6)
Paid holiday (Q45_1)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Paid sick leave (Q45_2)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Paid Maternity/Paternity Leave (Q45_3)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Parental leave or care leave (Q45_4)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Taking a day off unexpectedly (Q45_5)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Premiums and allowances to which I am entitled (e.g. shift bonus, travel allowance, hazard bonus) (Q45_6)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Fringe benefits to which I am entitled (e.g. eco vouchers, meal vouchers, etc.) (Q45_7)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Start of Block: insecurity of self-employed

Display This Question: to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = 8

Q252_z If I were to be ill for a long time, I would be in financial trouble.

- Completely disagree (1)
- Rather disagree (2)
- Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
- Mostly agree (4)
- Completely agree (5)
- No opinion (6)

Display This Question: to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = 8

Q253_z I can save enough money for my pension

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Rather disagree (2)
 - Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
 - Mostly agree (4)
 - Completely agree (5)
 - No opinion (6)
-

Display This Question: to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = 8

Q254_z I can save enough money to take annual vacation

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Rather disagree (2)
 - Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
 - Mostly agree (4)
 - Completely agree (5)
 - No opinion (6)
-

Display This Question: to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = 8

Q255_z I can save enough money to bridge a period with less work

- Completely disagree (1)
- Rather disagree (2)
- Partly agree, partly disagree (3)
- Mostly agree (4)
- Completely agree (5)
- No opinion (6)

Start of Block: training

Display This Question: not to self-employed (or artists)

If Q3 = NOT 8

Q46 I have completed training/education in the past 6 months, paid for or provided by my employer.

Yes (1)

no (2)

Start of Block: Moral distress

Display This Question: only to healthcare

If Q8_2 = 1 OR 2 OR 3 OR 4 OR 5

The following questions are about the quality of patient care. How often do you think that the following statements come true in your work?

	Very frequently (1)	Frequently (2)	Not very frequently (3)	Rarely (4)	Never (5)
My department is understaffed. (Q302_1)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I am not allowed to take action if I see an ethical problem. (Q302_2)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I have to carry out orders from my superiors that I consider unnecessary. (Q302_3)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I don't feel qualified for my tasks. (Q302_4)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I have to provide less than optimal care to reduce costs. (Q302_5)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I have to provide less than optimal care to save time. (Q302_6)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Start of Block: Psychological safety

To what extent do you agree with the following statements about your work environment?

	Strongly agree (1)	Agree (2)	Somewhat agree, somewhat disagree (3)	Disagree (4)	Strongly disagree (5)	No opinion (8)
It is difficult to signal a quality problem. (Q275_1)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
It is easy for personnel to ask questions when there is something that they do not understand. (Q275_2)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
In this work setting, it is difficult to discuss errors. (Q275_3)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
My suggestions about quality would be followed if I (Q275_4)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Start of Block: Commitment, Intent to stay

Display This Question: only to healthcare

If Q8_2 = 1 OR 2 OR 3 OR 4 OR 5

Q303 To what extent are you committed to your current job?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

From 0 'not at all' to 10 'completely' (1)

Display This Question: only to healthcare

If Q8_2 = 1 OR 2 OR 3 OR 4 OR 5

Q304 To what extent are you committed to your profession?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

From 0 'not at all' to 10 'completely' (1)

Start of Block: Calling

Please indicate the degree to which you believe the following statements describe you, using the following scale. Please respond with your career as a whole in mind. Try not to respond merely as you think you "should" respond; rather, try to be as accurate and as objective as possible in evaluating yourself.

	Not at all true of me (1)	Somewhat true of me (2)	Mostly true of me (3)	Absolutely true of me (4)
I believe that I have a calling to my work. (Q306_1)	☐	☐	☐	☐
Helping others is the primary motivation in my career. (Q306_2)	☐	☐	☐	☐
My career brings me purpose in life. (Q306_3)	☐	☐	☐	☐

Start of Block: job characteristics

The following statements are about other characteristics of your job. Please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree:

	Totally agree (1)	Rather agree (2)	Rather disagree (3)	Completely disagree (4)	No opinion (5)
My job requires me to learn new things. (Q52_1)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
My job demands a high degree of professional competence. (Q52_2)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
My job requires me to be creative. (Q52_3)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I get to do a lot of different things at work. (Q52_4)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I have the opportunity to learn new things at work. (Q52_5)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I have little freedom to decide how I do my job. (Q52_6)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I have a lot of say in what happens at work. (Q52_7)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

<p>My job gives me the freedom to make many decisions myself. (Q52_8)</p>	☐							
<p>My job requires me to work very quickly. (Q52_9)</p>	☐							
<p>My job requires me to work very hard. (Q52_10)</p>	☐							
<p>I don't have to do too much work. (Q52_11)</p>	☐							
<p>I have plenty of time to get my work done. (Q52_12)</p>	☐							
<p>My job requires a lot of physical effort. (Q52_13)</p>	☐							
<p>I often have to move or lift heavy loads in my work. (Q52_14)</p>	☐							
<p>I often have to work in an awkward position for extended periods of time." (Q52_15)</p>	☐							

I can quickly
find another
job if I want
to. (Q52_16)

There is a
chance that I
will soon lose
my job.
(Q52_17)

I feel
insecure
about the
future of my
job. (Q52_18)

Start of Block: unsocial and long hours

Can you indicate how many times you work on average per month at the following times?

	Always (1)	On a regular basis (2)	Sometimes (3)	Never (4)	I don't know (5)
I work ... between 5 pm and 10 pm. (Q53_1)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I work... at night. By night work we mean at least two hours of work between 8 pm and 5 am. (Q53_2)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I work... on a Saturday. (Q53_3)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I work... on a Sunday. (Q53_4)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I work... on a public holiday. (Q53_5)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I have to... work overtime. (Q53_6)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I have to be... standby. (Q53_7)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Start of Block: sliding hours

Q54 Do you use sliding hours? (can choose start and end time within certain limits)

Yes (1)

no (2)

Start of Block: abuse

During the past month, during your work, have you been subjected to:

	Yes (1)	no (2)	No opinion (3)
Verbal abuse (such as threats or degrading behavior) (Q55_1)	☐	☐	☐
Unwanted sexual attention (Q55_2)	☐	☐	☐
Physical violence (Q55_3)	☐	☐	☐
Discrimination (including for origin, gender, orientation,...) (Q55_4)	☐	☐	☐
Harassment or harassment (Q55_5)	☐	☐	☐
Being excluded (Q55_6)	☐	☐	☐

Start of Block: work-family

Q212 To what extent can you currently combine your working hours with your social and family obligations outside of work

- Very good (1)
- Good (2)
- Not good (3)
- Not good at all (4)
- No opinion (5)

Start of Block: general health

Q67 How is your health in general?

- Very good (1)
- Good (2)
- Reasonable (3)
- Bad (4)
- Very bad (5)
- No opinion (6)

Start of Block: specific health (multiple answers)

Q68 Have you suffered from the following health problems in the past six months?

	Yes (1)	no (2)	I don't know (3)
Backpain (1)	☐	☐	☐
Muscle aches in the shoulders, neck and/or upper limbs (2)	☐	☐	☐
Muscle aches in lower body parts (hips, legs, knees, feet, etc.) (3)	☐	☐	☐
Headache, eye pain (4)	☐	☐	☐
Stomach ache (5)	☐	☐	☐
Breathing difficulties (6)	☐	☐	☐
Injury(s), injury(s) (7)	☐	☐	☐
Depression or Anxiety (8)	☐	☐	☐
General fatigue (9)	☐	☐	☐
Insomnia or general sleep problems (10)	☐	☐	☐

Start of Block: WHO-5 well-being & activities

Please indicate for each of the five statements which is the closest to how you have been feeling over the last two weeks.

Q79 I have felt cheerful and in good spirits.

- All of the time (1)
 - Most of the time (2)
 - More than half of the time (3)
 - Less than half of the time (4)
 - Some of the time (5)
 - At one time (6)
-

Q80 I have felt calm and relaxed.

- All of the time (1)
 - Most of the time (2)
 - More than half of the time (3)
 - Less than half of the time (4)
 - Some of the time (5)
 - At one time (6)
-

Q81 I have felt active and vigorous.

- All of the time (1)
 - Most of the time (2)
 - More than half of the time (3)
 - Less than half of the time (4)
 - Some of the time (5)
 - At one time (6)
-

Q82 I woke up feeling fresh and rested.

- All of the time (1)
 - Most of the time (2)
 - More than half of the time (3)
 - Less than half of the time (4)
 - Some of the time (5)
 - At one time (6)
-

Q83 My daily life has been filled with things that interest me

- All of the time (1)
 - Most of the time (2)
 - More than half of the time (3)
 - Less than half of the time (4)
 - Some of the time (5)
 - At one time (6)
-

Q213 Over the past month, how many hours per week on average did you spend on the following activities outside of your paid work?

If no answer applies to you, enter 0.

- Zorgen voor en/of opvoeding van uw kinderen, kleinkinderen (1)

- Caring for elderly/disabled relatives (2)

- Cooking and household chores (3)

- Sport, culture or relaxation (4)

- Volunteer or Charity Work (5)

- Training or courses (6)

Start of Block: Psychological Capital

Below are statements that describe how you feel about yourself right now. Use the following scales to indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement.

Q121 I can think of many ways to reach my current goals

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Rather disagree (3)
 - Rather agree (4)
 - Agree (5)
 - Completely agree (6)
-

Q122 I can remain calm when facing difficulties because I can rely on my coping abilities

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Rather disagree (3)
 - Rather agree (4)
 - Agree (5)
 - Completely agree (6)
-

Q123 When I'm in a difficult situation, I can usually find my way out of it

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Rather disagree (3)
 - Rather agree (4)
 - Agree (5)
 - Completely agree (6)
-

Q124 The future holds a lot of good in store for me

- Completely disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Rather disagree (3)
 - Rather agree (4)
 - Agree (5)
 - Completely agree (6)
-

Q125 To what extent do you receive help and support from people you are close to when you need it?

- 0 Not at all (0)
- 1 (1)
- 2 (2)
- 3 (3)
- 4 (4)
- 5 (5)
- 6 Completely (6)
- Don't know (8)

Start of Block: political sentiments

We would like to ask a few questions about politics. How good do you think each of the following political systems would work for Belgium?

	Very good (1)	Fairly good (2)	Fairly bad (3)	Very bad (4)	Don't know (8)
Having a strong leader who does not have to bother with parliament and elections (Q352_1)	☐				
Having experts, not government, make decisions according to what they think is best for the country (Q352_2)	☐				
Having the army rule the country (Q352_3)	☐				
Having a democratic political system (Q352_4)	☐				

Start of Block: household

Q85 Which description best fits your current family situation?

- Single who lives alone (1)
- Single who lives with others (2)
- Single with children living at home (3)
- Single with children who (mainly) live elsewhere (4)
- Couple without children (5)
- Couple with children living at home (6)
- Couple with children who (mainly) live elsewhere (7)
- Lives with one or both parents (8)

Start of Block: personal income

Q87 How much is your own monthly net income from your main paid job?

0 600 1200 1800 2400 3000 3600 4200 4800 5400 6000

Monthly income from your main job in EURO
(on average) ()

Start of Block: income predictability

Q88 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statement: "I know well how much I will earn at the end of the month"?

- Totally agree (1)
- Rather agree (2)
- Rather disagree (3)
- Completely disagree (4)
- No opinion (5)

Start of Block: household income

Q89 What is your total net monthly family income, including the income of other family members, contributions from social benefits (such as unemployment, disability or illness), income from rent or interest and any others?

0 800160024003200400048005600640072008000

Monthly family income in EURO (average) ()

Start of Block: get by with household income

Q90 When you think about your household's total monthly income, can your household get by?

- Very easily (1)
- Easily (2)
- Fairly easily (3)
- With some difficulty (4)
- With difficulty (5)
- With great difficulty (6)
- No opinion (7)

Start of Block: opinion

Q93 We are interested in your opinion. Do you want to share something? Then write it below.
Thank you for your participation!
